

**“The translation of words specific to the national language is on the example of
Boburnoma”**

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Abstract: *Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur had a thirst for knowledge from his youth and was a person who stood out among his peers. Like all Timurid princes, Babur studied military education, jurisprudence, Arabic and Persian languages under the tutelage of special tutors and great religious scholars, read many historical and literary works, became interested in science and poetry. can rise to the level of generalization, and as a result, the ideas advanced in his works rise to the level of universal values.*

Key words: *Third Renaissance, scientific and creative heritage, literature, reading, dictionary, encyclopedia, science and innovations, artistic and journalistic works.*

In the years of independence, along with Navoi studies, a new scientific branch - Babur studies - was gradually formed in Uzbek literary studies. The science of Babur studies, which appeared in Western Europe in the 19th century and entered the stage of development in the 20th century, has not only been formed, even fundamental publications in this field such as "Encyclopedia of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur" and "Bibliography of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur" (Moscow, 2016). Eiji Mano (Japan), Magda Makhlouf (Egypt), Aziz Qayumov, Saidbek Hasanov (Uzbekistan), Mansura

Haydar (India), Ilza Sirtautas (USA), who participated in the international conference on the 534th anniversary of Babur's birth. Ramiz Asker (Azerbaijan) and Bilol Yujel (Turkey) unanimously acknowledged that the center of Babur studies has moved to Uzbekistan - Tashkent. Zakirjon Mashrabov, chairman of the international public fund named after Babur, has made special contributions in this field.

Since then, hundreds of articles and dozens of pamphlets and monographs on Babur studies have been written and published every year. In particular, the international conference on "The role of Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur's works in the history of world culture", which was held before the 535th anniversary of Babur's birth in 2017, and the publication of its materials under the name "Babur's Immortality" was also an important event in Babur studies. Last year's publication of Mirzo Kenjabek's new research on "Mubayyin" and "Volidiya" dedicated to the 539th anniversary of the birth of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur and the publication of the famous Babur scholar Hasan Qudratullayev's monographs "Literary and aesthetic world of Babur" were significant works in science. As "Boburnoma" is an encyclopedic work, it is like a treasure house with information of dozens of subjects. Whether a literary critic enters this treasure, a linguist digs into it, or a historian looks through it, he always comes across new information that the previous researcher did not see.

The main goal of the researcher in his new work is to approach "Boburnoma" from the point of view of typology. The author skillfully analyzed the texts about the events, persons and their fates in "Boburnoma" in comparison with the information in the books of the great writers and historians of that time, Alisher Navoi, Zayniddin Vasifi, Ghiyosiddin Khondamir, Abdurazzoq Samarkandi. At the same time, the

position, personality, talent, faith, and personal style of the authors were under observation. "Baburnoma" is a world-known and famous encyclopedia of Uzbek and all-Turkish literature. This memoir contains the culture, values, and unique characteristics of the peoples of Uzbekistan, Afghanistan, and India, as well as their nature, geography, animal and plant world. There is invaluable information about this rare source, which has been translated into various languages, and there is no shortage of excellent annotated dictionaries of the classic works. We are sure that there are experts who can do it.

To conduct scientific researches at the international level and announce their results, to create new scientific, artistic and journalistic works in order to study the scientific and creative heritage of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, statesmanship and military activities;

Creating high-quality media products and audiovisual works dedicated to the life and work of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, publishing them in local and foreign mass media, widely promoting them on the Internet and social networks;

Organization of educational events and roundtable discussions dedicated to the wide study and promotion of the work of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur in embassies of the Republic of Uzbekistan in foreign countries, Uzbek national cultural centers, compatriot societies.

In 2023, it was decided to create new performances based on the life and works of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, to organize competitions of the best songs performed with the poet's ghazals, and "Nazm va navo" status nights. In order to complete the feature film "Birth of the Tiger", which is being filmed on the basis of

the state order, dedicated to the childhood of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, it is necessary to work perfectly, to work to the extent that it can be delivered to the audience, to educate young people in the spirit of bravery, bravery, love for the country, and selflessness. several suggestions were made.

The complete third edition of "Babur Encyclopedia" on the life and work of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, the "Babur" book-album, as well as the dictionary of Babur's works, the perfect edition of Babur's divan; Measures are being taken to create a translation of the work "Boburnoma" into modern Uzbek and Karakalpak languages; to prepare and publish a series of scientific and popular books about the poet's works, his life and work under the heading "Baburga Armug'on".

The Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation together with the Union of Writers, the Republican Center for Spirituality and Enlightenment, the International Public Foundation named after Babur: a two-month state order for scientific research on the life and creative heritage of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur announced the selection of scientific projects in accordance with the requirements, made our youth even more happy. Let him ensure the gradual translation and publication of the works dedicated to the life and work of Babur Mirza from Uzbek to foreign languages and from foreign languages to Uzbek.

One of the unique figures who left an indelible mark in world history, Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur is known and famous all over the world as a great poet, encyclopedist, statesman and a skilled general. His incomparable scientific and creative heritage has a special place not only in the formation of our national culture and the literary and aesthetic thinking of our people, but also in the history of world literature, science and statecraft.

During the period of independence, extensive work was carried out on the comprehensive study of the life and activities of Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur, and the promotion of his works in our country and foreign countries. In particular, the poet's birthday - February 14 - is celebrated every year throughout our country as a holiday of literature and science. Many researches, national and international scientific conferences are regularly held in the field of philology. In the following years, huge statues of Babur Mirza were erected in Tashkent and Andijan, and the international public fund named after Babur and the book museum "Babur and World Culture" under its management are operating in Andijan, his birthplace, "Babur Encyclopedia". "Babur Kulliyati", "Babur. Baburidi. Bibliography" and the creation of the magazine "Babur and the World" were recognized as a great event in our cultural life.

Renovation of monuments and sites related to the name of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, including memorial complexes, and beautification of their territories; Restoration of manuscripts, ancient books, works of art and other cultural assets belonging to the heritage of Babur Mirza, creation of necessary conditions for their reliable preservation; the life, scientific and creative heritage of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, and unique collections related to the period in which he lived, which are kept in foreign countries to identify manuscripts and other cultural assets, bring their copies to Uzbekistan and continue research; such works are being carried out. These big achievements in the past time served to turn Uzbekistan into the center of world philology. Babur brought meaning to our nation with his life and work. As a chronicle of all completed works, the first personal dictionary in our country, i.e. "Babur Encyclopedia" was created. Along with Uzbek Babur scholars, Japanese,

Indian, Turkish, Afghan and European scholars also actively participated in the creation of this huge encyclopedia with 64 printed plates. Eiji Mano, a Japanese Babur scholar who has been studying Babur's work for forty years, assessed the encyclopedia as "an important guide for Babur scholars all over the world."

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